
Usage of Language Learning Strategy and Integrative Test Competence of Secondary Students

Marien A. Laureto¹, Andy Bon D. Dariagan², Maria Teresa Cosico³

^{1,2,3} Capiz state University Pontevedra Campus Filamer Christian University

ABSTRACT: This study endeavored to find out the relationship of the Usage of Language Learning Strategy and Integrative Test Competence among secondary students. The level of students' usage of language learning strategy is "moderate." This may have happened because at any age during the adolescent's stage, students' learning habit is not that established yet. Students have an "average" level of integrative test competence. Yet the male results reveal to low since their attitude towards language learning is not as enthusiastic as with female who got the result of average. The integrative test competence of the secondary students has an "average" level of competence. It is also revealed in the result that there is no significant difference in the level of the integrative test competence among the four grade levels. This could mean that students are not exposed to integrative testing. They are used to discrete testing that is often given by the teachers in every lesson. This could also mean that the level of difficulty appropriate to the level is not observed. Since it is expected that the higher the level, students get to learn more complex lessons that could help improve their competence with the language. The no significant relationship between language learning strategy and integrative test competence could mean that the language learning strategy awareness is not that established to students and that integrative test competence might be influenced by some other factors like exposure to such kind and the holistic approach to the language teaching.

KEYWORDS: Language learning strategy; Integrative test competence; English proficiency

1. INTRODUCTION

Language is based on the tenets of language teaching. So, it is imperative for language teachers to give tests, which are congruent, to what have been discussed in terms of methods and approaches applied by the teacher as a form of measuring the amount of learning the learners have taken in. A Cloze test is one type of test that will measure the communicative competence of the learners.

Nowadays, most students, particularly in the secondary level are observed to have poor performance in terms of their communicative competence, especially in understanding of the taken up lessons in the classroom. As observed, they do not give more importance in learning the language not knowing that by gaining communicative skills can help them obtain easy communication in any situations not just locally but also globally. Given their very hectic schedule at a very young age, students are forced to balance their time among academics and extra-curricular activities, friends and family that they get to have lesser time to focus on improving their English language skills. Moreover, they tend to be more passive since at this age, they just consider it as part of the curriculum that they have to study and not as a necessary skill that will help them in the future. Thus, the knowledge of the language learning strategy can be of help in improving or developing the proficiency and interest of the English Language.

Students may be conscious of how they learn, how they look at themselves as learners, and how they could acquire the learning skills to attain the competence that they need. They may be aware of the factors that affect their learning. They may have questions in mind that have to be given answers. If one is conscious on how he learns, then he can keep track of his progress in the acquisition of knowledge of the language. He may be able to find a way to cope with the demands of learning and to discover their need for improvement.

The researchers find it necessary to be able to use techniques and strategies in order to find out the strengths and weaknesses of the students when it comes to language proficiency. By this, teachers can intensify additional reinforcement of lessons and activities to aid students acquire the skills that they need. Thus, this study on language learning strategy is conducted.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Oxford (in Lee 2010) stated that strategies are particularly important for language learning "because they are tools for active, self-directed involvement, which is essential for developing communicative competence". Because of its significance, learning strategies have been extensively employed in the educational field. In defining the language learning strategy, "different researchers use different terms and different concepts."

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According to Bialystok (as cited by Ellis 2006), some strategies are behavioral and can be directly observed (e.g. asking a question for clarification), others are mental and behavioral but not easily observable (e.g. paraphrasing), while others are just mental (e.g. making mental translations for clarification while reading) and must be accessed through other means, such as through verbal report. Strategy frameworks have also been developed on the basis of degree of explicitness of knowledge and the kind of knowledge (e.g., linguistic vs. world knowledge, and form-focused vs. meaning-focused knowledge). In addition, strategies are sometimes labeled as belonging to “successful” or “unsuccessful” learners, when, in fact, the effectiveness of a strategy may depend largely on the characteristics of the given learner, the given language structure(s), the given context, or the interaction of these. Moreover, the very same learner may find that a given reading strategy (such as writing ongoing, marginal summaries while reading a text) works very well for the fifth paragraph of a given text but not for the sixth. The difficulty could result from the learner’s lack of vocabulary or grammatical knowledge, from the fact that the material is summarizer-unfriendly in that paragraph, from some distraction in the environment where the reading is going on (the classroom, the home, the library, etc.), or from some other cause.

Bialystok, as cited in Ellis (2006) defined language learning strategies as “optional means for exploiting available information to improve competence in a second language”.

Apparently, the term – language learning strategy has been toned and refined as more studies being conducted in the field.

Language learning strategies are viewed by Scarcella and Oxford as specific actions, behaviors, steps, or techniques – such as seeking out conversation partners, or giving oneself encouragement to tackle a difficult language task – used by students to enhance their own learning. Both the authors consider learners’ use of language strategies as conscious, purposely chosen and deliberate approach for facilitating learning. Learning strategies have comprehensively been defined by O’Malley and Chamot (as cited in Perez and Pingil, 2004) as focusing on selected aspects of new information, analyzing and monitoring information during acquisition, organizing or elaborating on new information during the encoding process, evaluating when it is completed, or assuring oneself that the learning will be successful as a way to allay anxiety.

According to Allen (as cited in Perez and Pingil 2004), language testing is the practice and study of evaluating the proficiency of an individual in using a particular language effectively.

In Education and Psychology, testing is an attempt to measure a person’s knowledge, intelligence, or other characteristics in a systematic way. There are many types of tests. Teachers give tests to discover the learning abilities of their students. They also give test to see how students have learned a particular subject. Some test help people choose a vocation, and other tests help them understand their own personality.

Testing is used in school to measure student achievement. State tests are given to students in a district once a year, based on their grade level and subject area. Classroom tests are given by individual teachers on a more regular basis and may include quizzes, mid-terms, chapter tests, and final exams, among others. Both types of tests give educators an idea of how well their students are learning the concepts presented to them in the classroom.

According to Go and Poesion (2010) integrative testing requires the candidate to combine many language elements in the completion of a task. This might involve writing a composition, making notes while listening to a lecture, taking a dictation, or completing a cloze passage. Integrative tests will tend to be a direct testing.

Sometimes an integrative item is really more a procedure than an item, as in the case of a free composition, which could test a number of objectives; for example, use of appropriate vocabulary, use of sentence level discourse, organization, statement of thesis and supporting evidence

3. MODEL, DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The main objective of this study was to find out the usage of language learning strategy and integrative test competence among the secondary students of Mater Carmeli School for the school year 2014- 2015.

To establish a meaningful result of this research, this study used the survey-correlational method to determine the level of usage of language learning strategy and the level of integrative testing competence among secondary students.

The independent variable was the usage of language learning strategy while the dependent variable in this study was the integrative test competence of the Secondary Students of Mater Carmeli School for the school year 2014-2015.

In the interpretation of data, descriptive statistical tools were used such as frequency count, percentage, and mean. For the analyses of inferential data, T-test, one way- Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and Pearson’s r were used. The alpha level of significance was set at 0.05.

The participants of this study were the officially enrolled one hundred seventy eight (178) students taken using the Sloven formula out of the total three hundred twenty nine (329) students of Mater Carmeli School for the school year 2014-2015.

The stratified random sampling was used in taking the number of participants. The distribution of the participants according to students’ year level included in the study is shown in Table 1.

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Table 1. Distribution of participants according to students' year level.

Participants	Total Population	SampleSize
Grade 7	86	46
Grade 8	82	45
Grade 9	79	42
Fourth Year	82	45
TOTAL	329	178

In order to determine the language learning strategy and integrative testing competence of the secondary students at Mater Carmeli School, the researchers administered the following questionnaires which were made up of three parts such as the profile of the respondents, language learning strategy, and integrative test competence.

Personalized Data Sheet. This part consisted of the personal information needed from the participant; the name, year level, and the sex.

The Strategy Inventory in Language Learning (SILL). This comprised of 50 items (Oxford, 1990). Each item described a language learning strategy and learners were asked to respond to the SILL items by indicating how often they employ these strategies by selecting one response out of five Likert scale options. In the SILL, language learning strategies were grouped into six categories for assessment: Memory strategies for storing and retrieving information; Cognitive strategies for understanding and producing the language ;Compensation strategies for overcoming limitations in language learning; Metacognitive strategies for planning and monitoring learning; and Affective strategies for controlling emotions, motivation, and social strategies for cooperating with others in language learning.

Using this instrument, the researcher was able to determine what type of learners were the respondents. This instrument also presented how the students learn.

The researcher asked the statistician, the chairman and a member of the panel to have it validated. After a discussion of the research topic and its goal, the Part I and II were validated.

The table below was used in interpreting the SILL result.

Scale	Description
4.5 to 5.0	Very High
3.5 to 4.49	High
2.5 to 3.49	Moderate
1.5 to 2.49	Low
1.0 to 1.49	Very Low

Integrative Test Competence. It is a standardized cloze test designed by Chavez- Oller, et al. (in Perez and Pingil, 2004), as the data-gathering instrument. According to Cerezo (2008), a cloze test is an integrative test that measures the examinee's skills in understanding meaning through the written context and in supplying the word that completes the meaning of a passage. In the instrument, respondents were asked to complete the passage by supplying the appropriate missing words that best complete the idea or essence of the passage.

The researcher asked the statistician, the chairman and a member of the panel to have it validated. The statistician and the chairman asked the researcher to simplify the test considering the student's level. After a discussion of the research topic and its goal, the Part III was validated.

The scale below were used for descriptive interpretation of data.

Scale	Description
39- 56	High
19- 38	Average
18	Low

Data- gathering Procedures

A permission to conduct the study was secured from the Principal of Mater Carmeli School. After the request was approved, the researcher asked the help of the advisers to have the respondents be excused from their classes for a period of time. Respondents were scheduled in to three batches to be accommodated. Each batch of respondents was gathered in one place. They were briefed about what the study was about and what is its purpose and how it will be able to help them. They were given the questionnaire. Each part and the purpose of the questionnaire were explained to them. They were only allowed to respond when made sure that the instruction was clear and there were no clarifications. The researcher asked a colleague to take pictures for documentation. Completed questionnaires was then gathered checked to make sure that no certain part was left unanswered before it was collected, checked for scores, tabulated and then submitted to the statistician for analysis.

Statistical Data Analysis Procedures

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Analysis of the data was undertaken using SPSS through the help of the statistician.

Frequency. This was used to determine the actual counts of the correct answers in the instrument. This was used in determining the level of integrative test competence of the students when grouped according to sex and year level.

Mean. It determined the averages of the subjects taken in certain categories. This was used in determining the level of integrative test competence of the students when grouped according to sex and year level.

T- test. This was used to know the significant difference of the language learning strategies of students and integrative test competence when grouped according to sex.

ANOVA or Analysis of Variance. This was used to find out the significant difference of the level of usage of language learning strategy and the level of integrative test competence among the students when grouped according to year level.

Pearson's r . It was used to find out the significant relationship of the usage of language learning strategy and of integrative test competence.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result reveals that the students have "moderate" level of usage in terms of memory, cognitive, compensation, metacognitive, affective and social. When grouped according to sex, and year level both categories fall into the "moderate level" of usage of language learning strategies. From this data, it was found out that both male and female have the same level of usage of language learning strategy as moderate. The result contradicts the outcome of the study of Green and Oxford (1995) and many more other studies that in the level of language learning strategy according to gender, they revealed that females use more language learning strategies than males.

Based also on the result, males use more of metacognitive, compensation and social strategy and less of memory and affective while the females practice more of cognitive, metacognitive and social and less with compensation and affective strategy.

The result of the female is comparable to the study done by Sy (1994). She found out that female students in Taiwan tended to use more cognitive, metacognitive and social strategies.

A study comparing more or less proficient learners in Taiwan (Lai, 2005) found out that more proficient learners used more metacognitive more cognitive and less memory skills than less proficient learners.

When grouped according to year level, the result shows moderate level of usage of language learning strategy for all levels. The findings also show the learners use more of social, more metacognitive and cognitive and less in affective and memory. The only prevailing level that has a different way of learning is from the Grade 9 that uses more of compensation strategy than all the other strategies.

This also signifies the result of the study of Takeuchi (2003) and Whartson (2000), that Asian students would create opportunities to practice English, apply specific strategies for different tasks, use different kinds of memory and cognitive strategies to help with their internalization and practical use of language.

From this it can be implied that students learn best when they are given an avenue to practice what they have learned in the lesson like through interactions. Males learn best through activities that could help them recall and apply stock knowledge and be able to relate them to the new one. This explains why inside the classroom, the male students find it very boring if teachers keep on repeating things and have them sit on their chairs and listen all throughout the class. Discrete teaching also is often applied in school most of the time. This is also measured through discrete testing thus making the whole process very dragging for the students. As noticed in their mathematics, they find it very interesting and exciting since it gave them the chance to apply metacognition. What they learned in the past is a continuation of what they are learning today and will still be relevant in the future lessons.

The result obtained from the level of usage of language learning strategy showed a narrow dispersion of the scores from the mean indicating the students' similarity in their level of usage of language learning strategy despite the differences of their year level. This is a total contrast of what was expected that the higher the level, the more they could establish certain language learning strategy that they should be using. This could also mean that the strategies that the teachers are using when it comes to teaching the language do not vary with regard to the year level that they are teaching thus giving the students less opportunity to enhance their own strategy usage. Teachers possibly do not know the learning styles applicable to the students they are handling thus there is less usage of the strategies that are supposedly effective for the learners.

The result explains the study of Yang (1999) that, although the students were aware of various language learning strategies, few of them actually reported using them since there is less opportunity for application. As a result of her research, Yang produced recommendations aimed at helping teachers adapt programs to students' needs more effectively.

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Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation of Usage Language Learning Strategy Among Sex and Year Levels

	Male		Female			
ULLS	Mean	Description	Rank	Mean	Description	Rank
Overall	3.05	Moderate		3.19	Moderate	
Memory	3.04	Moderate	5	3.09	Moderate	4
Cognitive	3.05	Moderate	4	3.31	Moderate	1
Compensation	3.10	Moderate	3	3.07	Moderate	6
Metacognitive	3.14	Moderate	1	3.30	Moderate	2.5
Affective	2.86	Moderate	6	3.08	Moderate	5
Social	3.11	Moderate	2	3.30	Moderate	2.5
	Grade 7		Grade 8			
Memory	3.27	Moderate	5	2.90	Moderate	4
Cognitive	3.36	Moderate	3	3.10	Moderate	1
Compensation	3.31	Moderate	4	2.88	Moderate	5
Metacognitive	3.45	Moderate	2	3.05	Moderate	2.5
Affective	3.18	Moderate	6	2.70	Moderate	6
Social	3.53	Moderate	1	3.05	Moderate	2.5
	Grade 9		Fourth Year			
Memory	2.98	Moderate	5	3.10	Moderate	4
Cognitive	3.17	Moderate	2	3.10	Moderate	4
Compensation	3.18	Moderate	1	2.97	Moderate	6
Metacognitive	3.15	Moderate	3	3.22	Moderate	1
Affective	2.88	Moderate	6	3.10	Moderate	4
Social	3.12	Moderate	4	3.13	Moderate	2

Scale	Description
4.5- 5.0	Very High
3.5- 4.49	High
2.5- 3.49	Moderate
1.5- 2.49	Low
1.0- 1.49	Very Low

The Table 2 shows that students have an “Average”(M= 20. 02) level of Integrative test competence. When grouped according to sex, male students have “Low” level (M= 18.31) and the female students have an “Average” level (M= 21.69). For year levels, the students have the result of “Average” competence when it comes to integrative test.

Based on the descriptive data, it is safe to infer that the female students perform better in Integrative test compared to male students. Though both fall in the descriptive as average yet the mean (Male, M= 18.31, Female, M= 21.69) yielded 3.38 difference.

Nowadays, male students are often engaged in online games, ball games and hanging out with friends. These make them less interested when it comes to academic tasks especially when it comes to English. They would just find English language as a subject and not as a useful tool in the future. They perceive it as just part of the academe and nothing more. Girls on the other hand, though still very much involved with gadgets, facebook and twitters, they still see the importance of performing well when it comes to their academics. And often times, they prefer staying at home and read books rather than just hanging around somewhere. They give more effort in learning the language since they think that the skill they acquire from it will make them look “higher in intellect” than the others. They perceive the English subject as a “status definition” thus, they remained focus and interested. Although they are more interested reading the books that are interesting and entertaining yet, these materials give them a clinch of the language itself. English comprises of endless letters-vocabulary, grammar, speaking, reading, etc. which the females find interesting. On the other hand, boys prefer numbers. Hence they see that English is a boring subject thus showing very poor performance when it comes to language test. Teachers on the other hand, failed to give activities that would elicit interest for the males to learn. They stick to the tradition not knowing or simply disregarding the male’s attitude towards language learning and unaware that they are slowly dragging behind. Thus, explaining the low level of performance when it comes to integrative test competence.

The result also reveals that there is no significant difference in the level of the integrative test competence among the four grade levels. This result suggests a total opposite of what was expected that the level of language exposure of the students’ increases as they go to the next level. The result, the integrative test competence of the students, reveals that it does not matter whether they belong to the lower grade level or the higher level. This implication will go back as to how the teachers give their tests. It is expected of them that as the level of the student increases, the higher the level of difficulty the students should be exposed. For example in Grade 7, the regular and irregular verb is introduced, in Grade 8, verb applications to different context should already be given emphasis. These days, the discrete testing is still very much used. In language learning, discrete testing does not often measure what it ought to measure. It only focuses on in one aspect of the lesson. Language is not delivered by chunks but as a whole. Therefore,

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it should be tested holistically as well. This explains that students would score high in a discrete test but they find integrative test as very complicated.

The result tied up with the study of Cohen (in Perez and Pingil, 2004) that integrative tests are both direct and communicative. They are concerned not only with the different aspects of knowledge but also the testee's ability to demonstrate in actual situations. They attempt to focus on the expression and understanding of the functional use of language rather than on the more limited mastery of language found from in discrete point tests. Learners should be exposed to it as a way of measuring how much they have learned.

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation of Integrative Test Competence Among Sex and Year Levels

Male		Female	
Mean	Description	Mean	Description
18.31	Low	21.69	Average
Grade 7		Grade 8	
20.02	Average	19.84	Average
Grade 9		4 th Year	
20.64	Average	19.64	Average

Scale	Description
39- 56	High
19- 38	Average
1- 18	Low

The t- test result in Table 3a yielded p= value of .115 which is greater than 0.5 level of significance. Hence, there is no significant difference in the level of usage of language learning strategy of students when grouped according to sex.

The result in table 3a implies that the level of language learning strategy of the students has no difference. It means, for both the male and female, that they are the same when it comes to language learning strategy usage maybe because the students' exposure to the strategies and idea of them are the same. They really expose themselves to certain strategies since these are easier ways for them to be able to learn. This could also indicate that the students may be using certain strategy yet they are not aware of it that it as a strategy already. They know that these strategies exist yet they do not apply that much or as often as they should be since they are still learning the language.

This connotes to the study of Macaro's (2009) The relationship between knowing and doing when he said that there are ideas that you know that is there and you are aware of its usage yet you do not use it often though you know it is there. It is the same through with the language learning strategy. A student might know that reading is a good way to learn vocabulary but he may have a bad habit of being so lazy when it comes to reading or may he may find the activity a bore yet, he has the knowledge that for him to improve his vocabulary he must use this certain strategy.

Table 3. a t-test of Usage of Language Learning Strategy Between Sex

Sex	N	Mean	SD	t	df	Sig
male	88	3.05	.53	-1.58	177	.115
female	91	3.19	.64			

Table 3b shows that a p= .009 is lesser than .05 level of significance. Hence, there is a significant difference in the level of usage of the language learning strategy when grouped according to year level.

This indicates that regardless of what year level the student is in, may it be from the lower level, Grade 7 and Grade 8, or from the higher level, Grade 9 and Grade 10, the level of usage of the language learning strategy is aligned to what they are expected.

This indicates that for each year level there is an increase in the level usage of language learning strategy. It simply indicates that in every year level, there are varied strategies that student use for them to learn the language. Maturity towards the environment could be an indicator of this. As students aged or go to the higher level, they learn many things and they are exposed to many activities already that they could make use of when it comes to learning. Teachers also help them gain more exposure to many learning strategies inside the class while having their lessons. This is already a good indicator that as the learners grow, they get equipped with methods that would best help them towards facing higher level of competencies as they go through with their studies. This is also a good indication that the students do not stagnate in their skills and ideas and instead, they seek ways to be able to adapt to the next level thus improving themselves when it comes to usage of strategy especially in language learning.

The result adheres to the study of Green and Oxford (1995) that more proficient language learners employed more types and more frequent use of strategies than less proficient learners.

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Table 3. b Analysis of Variance of Usage of Language Learning Strategy Among Year Levels

	Mean		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.
Grade 7	3.35	Bet Grps	3.96	3	1.32	4.003	.009
Grade 8	2.95	W/in Grps	57.68	175	.33		
Grade 9	3.08	Total	61.64	178			
4th Year	3.10						

Table 4a shows that the t- test result yielded a P= value of .001 which is lesser than .05 level of significance. Hence, significant difference exists in the level of Integrative Testing Competence of the male and female students.

It implies that female students perform better in integrative test compared to the male students. Perhaps, since the male students are often very passive when it comes to learning the language, their competence also deteriorates. Often times, their attitude towards the language is not as enthusiastic as that of the girls who finds the language very interesting. Their inclination towards the environment also affects their way of thinking and actions. Female students would really get very interested when it comes to discussions of one of the major areas in English, the literature, while the boys find it really boring, thus, affecting their performance as well. Grammar is also another. Female ones treasure every rule since they find it very embarrassing when they use the language and their grammar is in chaos, while the male students do not care about the structures at all as long as they are able to express their thoughts using the language and at times, since they lack the knowledge in dealing with word relationships, they opt to speak in vernacular as an escape. All these may attribute to poor performance in the integrative test competence of the male students and help improve the level of competence of the females.

The result negates the study of Giesen (as cited in Gala, 2003) in South Africa with various EFL learners that uncovered evidence that metacognitive strategies are often strong predictors of second language proficiency. This is a total opposite of the result of the male integrative test competence who is a majority of metacognitive learners.

Grounded on the result, the null hypothesis, there is no significant difference in the level integrative test competence according to sex, is rejected.

Table 4. a t-test of Integrative Test Competence Between Sex

Sex	Mean	SD	t	df	Sig
male	18.31	6.68	-3.43	177	.001
female	21.69	6.54			

The ANOVA result in Table 4b shows a p value of .916 which is greater than .05 level of significance. Hence, there is no significant difference in the level of integrative test competence of Grade 7 to Fourth year.

It infers that when it comes to the integrative test competence, the level of the secondary students is the same regardless of the year level they are in.

The result could somehow attest to the theory of Bialystok as cited by Ellis (2006), employing strategies are sometimes labeled as belonging to “successful” or “unsuccessful” learners, and that the effectiveness of a strategy may depend largely on the characteristics of the given learner, the given language structure (s), the given context, or the interaction of all these. Therefore, regardless of what level the students are in, the level of usage of language learning strategy relies deeply on the learner. In contrast to the result in table 1 that metacognitive learners are proficient learners, basically, the result of an effective usage of language learning depends on the kind of learner.

This may mean that, first; the students are not used to this kind of tests. They always perceive that since the lesson in English is served per chunk, they thought it should also be used that way. Second, teachers may often give discrete test measures student’s learning by portion that it forfeits the essence of learning the language which should be taken holistically. Students may find integrative testing very confusing since their exposure to it is minimal. This may also mean that language teachers per year level were not able to align their competency according to standard and increase the level of difficulty of the lesson thus their level when it comes to language learning is also the same. Third, it may be contributed to student’s poor understanding of the structure of the language thus explains the difficulty which could also be attributed to the teachers method in delivering the lesson.

This result negates the study of Lai, (2005) that found put that more proficient learners used more metacognitive, cognitive and less memory skills than less proficient learners.

The null hypothesis, there is no significant difference in the level of integrative test competence among the secondary students, is accepted.

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Table 4. b Analysis of Variance of Integrative Test Competence Among Year Levels

	Mean		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.
Grade 7	20.02	Bet Grps	24.02	3	8.006	.170	.916
Grade 8	19.84	W/in Grps	8216.84	175	46.95		
Grade 9	20.64	Total	8240.86	178			
4th Year	19.64						
Total	20.03						

Table 5 shows that there is no significant relationship between language learning strategy and integrative test competence since the $p = .78$ is greater than $.05$.

This means that the language learning strategy that the students use in learning the language does not influence their integrative test competence.

This study may give us an idea that language learning strategy may not always be adherent to improve students' competency when it comes to learning the language as well as their level when it comes to integrative test, in the same way that integrative test competence may not be influenced at all regardless of what strategy a learner or a student may apply or use when it comes to language learning.

The result do not keep to the theory of Oxford (1990) that claims that language learning strategies are tools for active, self-directed involvement and are essential for developing communicative competence.

Based on the result, the null hypothesis, there is no significant relationship between the usage of language learning strategy and integrative test competence, is accepted.

Table 5. Pearson r Between Usage of Language Learning Strategy and Integrative Test Competence

	r	Sig
Usage of Language Learning Strategy and Integrative Test Competence	0.021	0.785

5. CONCLUSIONS

Living in the world of today when technology is a highlight yet having the students' language strategy as moderate is still considerable. This means that students will to learn is still balanced somehow yet since they view language learning as just a mere subject and not as a lifelong tool for communication, they do not exert effort to improve their way of learning even more. They are just contented on what was given and fed to them. Teachers' unawareness of the importance of usage of strategies in the class could have deterred them as well and limit themselves of what is just accepted and needed, nothing beyond that.

The students have somehow similarities in strategies when it comes to language learning with the metacognitive and social strategies prevailing and less on affective and memory.

Students' level of usage of language learning strategy as moderate may have happened because at any age during the adolescent's stage, students' learning habit is not that established yet. They are not aware of the strategies or styles that they have when it comes to learning the language since they just find it as a mere subject to deal with like all the other subjects. This could also mean that their exposure to certain strategies is not that much that they could not identify what strategy they could really stick in when learning. Since the school is situated in a rural area, most of the teachers are not that exposed to technologies coming out, the reason why some stay to be in a traditional way of teaching thus limiting student's exposure to various activities that could have helped them to improve even more. This could also mean that language teachers' instruction do not vary that much. Students are not thoroughly exposed to certain strategy that may help them improve their language acquisition. Though they are on the different grade levels, they have similarities when it comes to language learning and that is the more on the usage of social, metacognitive and cognitive strategies and less of affective and memory. Compensation strategy is best used by the grade 9 students.

As a whole, students integrative test competence results to average. Yet the males result reveal to low since their attitude towards language learning is not as enthusiastic as the females who have the result of average. The females also have the language learning strategies that according to studies are most likely to be proficient in language learning. In the class, the boys are very lacks since they find the language learning not challenging and they find this so feminine. They do not see the importance of acquiring the language thus they tend to be very passive. They do class activities only because they have to and not because they could see the benefits in doing so. Language teachers as well do not exert effort to elicit the males' interest to the lesson. They find it as a natural thing for the boys that they do not care at all as long as they are there and they are not making any nuisance in the class.

The Integrative test competence of the secondary students at Mater Carmeli School from Grade 7 to Fourth Year has an "average" level of competence. It is also revealed in the result that there is no significant difference in the level of the integrative test competence among the four grade levels. This could mean that students are not exposed to integrative testing. They are used to discrete testing that was often given by the teachers in every lesson. This could also mean that the level of difficulty appropriate to

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the level is not observed. Since it is expected that the higher the level, students get to learn more complex lessons that could help improve their competence with the language.

That there is no significant relationship between language learning strategy and integrative test competence could be supposed that the language learning strategy awareness is not that established to students and that integrative test competence might be influenced by some other factors like exposure to such kind and the holistic approach to the language teaching.

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